

AN OVERVIEW OF DEEP LEARNING IN MEDICAL IMAGE PROCESSING USING CNN

Rashia Subashree R^{1*}, Nancy Jasmine Goldena²

¹Research Scholar, Reg.no: 23211202282006, Department of Computer Application and Research Centre, Sarah Tucker College (Autonomous), Tirunelveli
E-mail: rasiyakrishnan@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, Department of Computer Application and Research Centre Sarah Tucker College (Autonomous), Tirunelveli
E-mail: nancy_lordwin@rediffmail.com

Received: April 05, 2024, **Accepted:** May 10, 2024, **Online Published:** June 15, 2024

ABSTRACT

Deep Learning, a pinnacle of Machine Learning, has ignited excitement for revolutionary advances in healthcare. Its success in various pattern recognition applications, including computer vision, natural language processing, speech, and image identification, has made it a potent tool across industries. In healthcare, Deep Learning is transforming medical image analysis, which is crucial for early diagnosis, treatment planning, and overall healthcare management. Analyzing unique patient data generates personalized treatment plans tailored to individual traits and reactions. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), central to Deep Learning, have significant applications in healthcare, especially in interpreting structured grid data like medical images. CNNs excel in tasks such as image classification, object detection, semantic segmentation, and disease diagnosis by learning hierarchical representations and extracting features to recognize complex patterns in medical images. This paper explores the basic concepts, potential, challenges, and advancements of CNNs. It aims to guide future research, enhance reproducibility, and deepen understanding of CNNs' transformative impact on medical image processing, synthesizing collective knowledge in healthcare.

Keywords: Deep Learning, CNN, Convolutional Neural Networks, Image Classification, Image Segmentation, Medical Image.

1. Introduction

Deep Learning is an area of machine learning that uses multi-layered neural networks, or deep neural networks, to imitate the human brain's sophisticated decision-making capacity. Deep Learning powers the majority of artificial intelligence (AI) in our lives today. Medical imaging is essential to modern healthcare because it allows doctors to identify and diagnose a wide range of illnesses, from fractures to tumours [0]. However, manually interpreting these images can be time-consuming and prone to human error. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) can help overcome these challenges by using Deep Learning to automatically identify patterns and features in large volumes of labelled medical images. The basic architecture of CNNs consists of Convolutional Layers, Pooling Layers, and Fully Connected Layers. Convolutional layers are critical for capturing spatial hierarchies and patterns in images. Using filters, these layers progressively acquire more complex representations by identifying local features in the input image. Pooling layers then reduce the spatial dimensions of the features while retaining all relevant information [0]. This hierarchical feature extraction enables CNNs to understand intricate structures in medical images, facilitating accurate

diagnosis and analysis. CNNs automatically extract the most relevant features from the image data, unlike conventional techniques that require manual feature engineering by humans. This reduces reliance on human expertise and mitigates bias [0]. The ability to learn directly from data is a major strength of CNNs. In training, the network optimizes its ability to identify patterns relevant to the particular medical imaging task by adjusting its parameters based on the input data. CNN performance is further improved through transfer learning, which uses a large dataset of pre-trained models to fine-tune them for a specific medical imaging application. This is especially useful when labelled medical data is scarce [0]. CNNs can match or even exceed the accuracy of human experts. By automating image processing tasks, CNNs can significantly reduce the workload for radiologists and other medical professionals, freeing them to focus on more complex aspects of patient care. CNNs have proven highly effective for medical imaging applications, including organ segmentation, disease classification, and tumour detection. For example, CNNs can automatically detect subtle anomalies in medical scans, enabling earlier intervention in cancer diagnosis. They also excel at image segmentation, which is critical for treatment planning and surgical

guidance since it allows precise delineation of organs or structures of interest [0]. A key advantage of CNNs in medical imaging is transfer learning. Smaller medical image datasets can be used to fine-tune CNN models already trained on larger datasets like ImageNet. Even with limited data, the

model can adapt and specialize in analyzing medical images with improved performance due to this knowledge transfer. As Deep Learning advances, CNNs are poised to transform medical imaging, enhancing diagnostic accuracy and contributing to personalized healthcare [0].

Fig 1: Basic Structure of CNN in Deep Learning

2. Literature Survey:

The objective of “Convolution Neural Network for Breast Cancer Detection and Classification Using Deep Learning” [0] illustrated a Deep Learning model called BCCNN to detect and classify breast cancers into eight classes using breast cancer MRI images. The eight classes included benign adenosis, benign fibroadenoma, benign phyllodes tumour, benign tubular adenoma, malignant ductal carcinoma, malignant lobular carcinoma, malignant mucinous carcinoma, and

malignant papillary carcinoma. The proposed BCCNN model and five pre-trained Deep Learning models (Xception, InceptionV3, VGG16, MobileNet, ResNet50) trained on ImageNet were evaluated on each of the datasets individually, resulting in a total of 30 experiments. The performance of the models was measured using metrics like F1-score, recall, precision, and accuracy. The results showed that the BCCNN model achieved the highest classification F1-score accuracy of 98.28%, followed by ResNet50

at 98.14%, while MobileNet had the lowest accuracy of 93.98.

The paper “Deep Learning for ECG Arrhythmia Detection and Classification: An Overview of Progress for Period 2017–2023” [0] by Ansari Y and co-author discusses the importance of identifying cardiac irregularities for early detection, diagnosis, and prevention of cardiovascular diseases. It highlights the role of Electrocardiography (ECG) as the benchmark approach and the potential benefits of automatic detection of abnormalities. The paper surveys and compares Deep Learning (DL) architectures used in ECG arrhythmia detection, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Multilayer Perceptron’s (MLPs), Transformers, and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). They provide a roadmap for emerging researchers to expedite the acclimation process and develop efficient algorithms for detecting ECG anomalies using DL models.

The researchers Raimundo and co-author have proposed an Innovative Faster R-CNN-Based Framework for Breast Cancer Detection in MRI”[0] have an innovative methodology for preprocessing patients' cases using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). This approach minimizes background noise, reduces the number of slices per patient needed for benchmarking,

and reduces computational time for training ML/DL detection models. They developed a full lifecycle framework for training and testing “Faster R-CNN-based Deep Learning models” and successfully validated it using an annotated dataset, DukeBC. The models achieved a satisfactory mean accuracy of 94.46% with a standard deviation of 2.43%.

The study “Machine Learning and Deep Learning Approach for Medical Image Analysis: diagnosis to Detection” by Rana M and Bhushan M [0]. Reviews the applications of machine learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) in detecting and classifying diseases from medical images. The study compares different ML and DL approaches, imaging modalities, evaluation techniques, and datasets. Experiments on MRI data show that Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and random forests (RF) performed better than other algorithms, with CNN achieving 97.6% accuracy and RF 96.93% accuracy. Both classical ML and DL approaches are extensively used in healthcare due to their data uncertainty handling capabilities.

Unaiza Sajid and co-author have proposed “Breast cancer classification using deep learned features boosted with handcrafted features experiments” [0] were done on an MRI dataset to compare the performance of ML classifiers with DL

models. This study intends to assist healthcare practitioners in selecting the optimal strategy for diagnosing a certain condition with high accuracy and in less time. The context does not give sufficient information to address any particular queries concerning frameworks for breast cancer detection or categorization.

The paper “An Intelligent Auxiliary Framework for Bone Malignant Tumor Lesion Segmentation in Medical Image Analysis” by Zhan, Xiangbing, and co-author [0] presents a new intelligent auxiliary framework network (SEAGNET) for precise bone malignant tumour segmentation. To grasp the uncertainty of the border feature space, the network employs a BKPS module for supervised learning and mixed attention. Validated on a real-world medical picture dataset, the technique increases diagnostic accuracy in clinical workflow, lowers reliance on manual diagnosis, saves time, and improves medical process efficiency.

3. Architecture of CNN in Deep Learning

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs, or ConvNets) are multi-layer

neural networks designed to detect visual patterns in pixel pictures. 'Convolution' is used in CNN to refer to the mathematical function. CNNs function by applying convolution and pooling layers to an input image or video. It is a linear operation in which two functions are multiplied to form a third function that indicates how one function's shape may be altered by the other. [0] An input layer is usually where a CNN's architecture starts, receiving an image's raw pixel data, as shown in Fig 2. The building blocks of convolutional layers use filters to search for and identify local patterns, which allows them to capture hierarchical characteristics efficiently. Network learning of complex representations is improved by integrating the concept of non-linearity via activation functions such as ReLU. Computational efficiency and translation invariance are improved by subsequent pooling layers that decrease spatial dimensionality. Regression or classification tasks need the consolidation of retrieved features, which is generally accomplished by completely linked layers in the final layers. [0]

Fig 2: Basic Architecture of CNN

3.1. 2D Architecture Convolutional Neural Networks

2D Convolutional Neural Networks, or 2D CNNs, are specialized Deep Learning architectures designed to handle two-dimensional input, often images. Among its strong aspects are image segmentation, picture categorization, and object recognition.

Convolutional layers: These layers extract characteristics from incoming data by applying filters or kernels.

Layers for pooling: By downsampling the input's spatial dimensions, these layers lower computing costs and highlight the most crucial information.

Fully connected layers: Conventional layers of a neural network that link each neuron between layers.

They are used in image classification tasks, which allow illnesses to be recognized from individual photos, and object detection tasks, which allow abnormalities like tumours to be precisely localized. Furthermore, 2D CNNs help segment images and help distinguish between organs or structures for more in-depth examination [0]. A common use of transfer learning is the fine-tuning of pre-trained models on huge datasets for particular medical imaging applications with sparsely labelled data. 2D CNNs greatly increase the accuracy and efficiency of medical picture interpretation, which eventually leads to better patient care and diagnostic results despite obstacles such as data scarcity and the requirement for careful tuning.

Fig 3: Architecture of 2D CNN

3.1.1 Utility of 2D CNN

- **Disease Detection and Diagnosis:** CNNs are able to help medical practitioners with early diagnosis and treatment planning by analyzing pictures to detect anomalies such as tumours, lesions, or fractures.
- **Image Segmentation:** Segmenting clinical images into discrete areas for in-depth examination is known as image segmentation. Dividing and delineating several organs on a CT image to facilitate surgical planning [0].
- **Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD):** CNNs can provide radiologists with a second opinion by pointing out questionable areas in pictures and recommending more research.
- **Longitudinal Patient Monitoring:** Monitoring a patient's changes and development over time to track the evolution or regression of lesions throughout many imaging scans.

3.2. 3D Architecture Convolutional Neural Networks

In the domain of medical imaging, three-dimensional Convolutional Neural Networks, or 3D CNNs, have drawn a lot of interest and have been shown to be beneficial. It is a more sophisticated form of the conventional 2D CNN architecture designed to handle volumetric data, including 3D medical pictures and CT or MRI scans [0]. Through the provision of more precise and context-aware analyses of volumetric data, 3D CNNs significantly advance medical imaging by aiding in the better segmentation, localization, and identification of diseases.

3D convolutional layers: These layers take responsibility for both the spatial and temporal dimensions when applying 3D filters on volumetric input.

3D Pooling Layers: Layers for 3D pooling are two-dimensional versions of 2D pooling layers.

Temporal layers: In sequential data, these layers represent temporal interdependence.

In the field of video classification, these networks are very useful for identifying complex movements and events in moving sequences. They are especially skilled at recognizing patterns across time because of their capacity to record both temporal and spatial data, which improves their accuracy in detecting complicated activities [0]. When used on volumetric medical data or dynamic sequences, 3D CNNs' ability to comprehend 3D spatial connections and temporal dynamics highlights its importance in a wide range of cutting-edge technologies.

Fig 4: Architecture of 3D CNN

3.2.1 Utility of 3D CNN

- **Analyse volumetric data:** The analysis of three-dimensional medical imaging, such as CT or MRI scan volumes. 3D CNNs are used in volumetric scans to identify and segment tumours.
- **Recognize gestures:** Identifies hand or body motions in a series of frames to enable applications in sign language recognition and human-computer interaction.
- **3D Image Reconstruction:** Used medical scans to create three-dimensional pictures. Combining a number of 2D X-ray pictures to create 3D reconstructions [0].
- **Long-Term Research:** Examine how a patient's medical photos evolve and alter over time. Repeated MRI images were used to track the development of lesions.

3.3. Comparison of 2D and 3D CNN

3.3.1 Dimension of Data:

- **2D CNNs:** Ideal for image-based applications, they process input that resembles a 2D grid.

- **3D CNNs:** Manage 3D volumetric data, sequentially obtaining spatial and temporal information.

3.3.2 Uses:

- **2D CNNs:** Proficient in segmentation, object identification, and picture classification.
- **3D CNNs:** Perfect for volumetric data analysis, medical imaging, and video categorization.

4. CNNs in Medical Image Classification and Image Segmentation

4.1. Image Classification

CNN-based image classification has gained a significant improvement in illness diagnosis, therapy preparation, and general patient care. They are able to carry out the activities according to their capacity to automatically extract and identify complex patterns from medical pictures, such as X-rays, CT scans, and MRIs.

Data preparation is the first step of a methodical procedure that uses Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to classify medical images. Preprocessing is applied to medical image datasets during this step to guarantee consistency and remove noise. [0] Common techniques include augmentation, normalization, and scaling to improve the variety of the training set and build the groundwork for strong model training.

4.2. Image Segmentation

CNNs are essential to medical image segmentation because they provide cutting-edge results across a range of applications. In order to increase the precision, resilience, and interpretability of these models in the context of medical imaging, researchers are still looking at novel architectures and approaches [0]. Their method involves a sequence of convolutional and pooling layers that extract features and lower dimensionality, all the while retaining spatial information that is essential for segmentation. In medical imagery, such as tumors in MRI scans or blood arteries in angiograms, this enables CNNs to discern between various tissues and structures with effectiveness [0]. With the help of a robust hierarchical feature extraction technique, CNNs often use an encoder-decoder design, such as the popular U-Net model. This architecture makes it possible to extract complex characteristics from medical pictures, which helps with accurate segmentation. Transfer learning, which uses pre-trained CNN models that have been refined on smaller medical datasets, is a popular method for overcoming the problem of little annotated medical data.

Table 1: Comparison between the application of CNNs in image classification and segmentation for Lung Cancer Detection in chest X-rays/CT scans

Dimension	Image Classification	Image Segmentation
Task	Labelling CT and X-ray images	Image segmentation for in-depth examination
Aim	Identify the presence or absence of lung cancer	Identify and classify lung cancer tumours
Output	Single label (e.g., cancer or non-cancer)	Segmentation of pixels to identify tumour areas
Training Data	Labelled dataset with images and corresponding diagnoses	Labelled dataset with images and pixel-wise annotations
Architecture	Uses 2D CNNs	Use 2D or 3D CNNs, U-Net, or similar architectures
Applications	Screening and initial diagnosis	Precise tumour localization, treatment planning
Example Use Case	Recognizing lung cancer in images obtained from X-rays	CT scan segmentation of lung tumours for surgical planning

The above table compares the application of CNNs in image classification and segmentation for Lung Cancer Detection in chest X-rays/CT scans [0].

5. Benefits and challenges:

5.1. Advantage of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)

An Artificial Neural Network type that is frequently used for object and image recognition and classification is called a Convolutional Neural Network, or CNN. It is a backbone for image processing techniques in Deep Learning. It has demonstrated remarkable efficacy across diverse domains, such as medical image processing.

➤ **Increased Precision and Sensitivity:**

The ability of Deep Learning to analyze massive amounts of data and

efficiently perform multiple calculations makes it incredibly scalable. They provide flexibility and accessibility deployment on edge devices and cloud platforms. CNNs demonstrate better precision and sensitivity in a range of medical imaging tasks, including organ segmentation, disease categorization, and tumour identification. Predictive and early diagnosis may result from this.

➤ **Real-time Processing:**

Hardware breakthroughs combined with efficient CNN architectures make real-time

processing of medical images possible. This is especially helpful in healthcare settings where prompt and precise diagnosis is crucial.

➤ **Autonomous Feature Acquisition:**

Deep Learning CNN systems can automatically extract features from data such as cancers, lesions, and anatomical structures, reducing the need for human feature engineering. This is especially improving picture identification in situations where defining features could be challenging. This can lessen the workload for medical personnel and increase the effectiveness of medical workflows.

➤ **Feature Extraction:** An essential step in comprehending and evaluating visual data is feature extraction. CNNs are very good at extracting spatial and hierarchical characteristics from images, which makes them useful for tasks like segmentation, object recognition, and image classification. CNNs are made to automatically extract feature representations in a hierarchical structure from incoming data. This means that CNNs can automatically recognize and extract pertinent elements from complicated images, which aids in the detection of abnormalities and patterns in medical imaging.

➤ **Transfer Learning:** CNN models that have already been trained on huge datasets, such as ImageNet, can be adjusted for particular medical imaging applications. Furthermore, in situations when the additional domain has a smaller quantity of labelled data than the first, transfer learning enables the model to use the information obtained from one to enhance performance in the latter.

➤ **Integration with Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS):** Integrating CNNs with CDSS enables healthcare practitioners to obtain supplementary data and perspectives when making decisions. As a result, planning and diagnosis may become more informed.

5.2. Disadvantage of CNN

Medical image analysis is one application where Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have demonstrated great potential and effectiveness. However, there are unique hurdles that CNNs must overcome in this field. Some of these challenges include:

➤ **Restricted Access to Data:** Privacy issues frequently restrict the number of medical datasets, and obtaining labelled data to train strong models can be difficult. Small datasets might not fully reflect the variety of medical issues and might cause overfitting.

➤ **Explainability and Interpretability:**

Deep Learning Algorithms sometimes have black-box problems that make it difficult to debug and understand how they make decisions. CNNs are frequently regarded as “black-box” models, which makes it difficult to understand their conclusions, particularly in vital medical applications where knowing the logic behind a diagnosis is essential. Gaining the confidence of medical experts requires ensuring interpretability and explainability. [0]

➤ **Estimating Confidence and**

Uncertainty: In medical applications, providing CNN predictions with confidence levels and uncertainty estimations is essential. Clinical decision-making requires an understanding of a model's prediction confidence level, particularly in situations when errors may have serious repercussions.

➤ **Training takes a long time:** The number of datasets, the intricacy of model topologies, and the requirement for sophisticated hardware all contribute to the length of time required for neural network training. Regularisation, optimization techniques, and hyperparameter tuning are some of the other factors that add to

the length. Minimizing training time without sacrificing model performance is possible using effective methods, including transfer learning, parallelization, and data augmentation.

➤ **Limited effectiveness for sequential**

data: Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) tend not to be particularly effective at processing sequential data because of their fixed input sizes and poor temporal dependency capturing capabilities. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) or Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs) are commonly used for sequence-related tasks due to their better memory and sequential modelling capabilities.[1]

6. Applications of CNN:

➤ **Disease Diagnosis:**

CNNs are essential for using medical image analysis to diagnose disorders. They may be used to find patterns linked to illnesses, including multiple sclerosis, Alzheimer's disease, and different kinds of cancer.

➤ **Image Classification:**

CNNs are utilized for classifying restorative pictures into diverse categories, such as diverse sorts of tissues, organs, or neurotic conditions. This helps in robotizing the examination of huge datasets and

progressing symptomatic exactness.

[0]

➤ **Detection and Segmentation:**

Medical image analysis techniques, including MRI, CT, and PET scans, employ CNNs to identify and segment tumours. Their usefulness in diagnosing and planning treatment involves helping radiologists determine whether, where, and how big tumours are.

➤ **Image Registration**

Certain medical images, such as preoperative and intraoperative images, can be aligned and registered using CNNs. The planning and navigation of surgery depend on this.

➤ **Automated Pathology Detection**

CNNs are utilized in histopathology slides to identify abnormal characteristics automatically. This involves detecting malignant cells, assessing the shape of the tissue, and supporting pathologists in their diagnostic evaluations.

➤ **Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD)**

CNN is used in CAD systems to assist radiologists in the interpretation of medical images. These systems can provide additional information, highlight abnormalities, and improve the efficiency of the diagnostic process.

7. Research Openings

Convolutional Neural Networks, or CNNs, seem to have an optimistic future in medical imaging. They have the potential to improve diagnostic precision and stimulate innovation in healthcare significantly. As technology develops, CNN integration with cutting-edge methods like federated learning and explainable AI may improve openness and cooperative information exchange among healthcare organizations. Further enhancing the generalization and resilience of CNNs may be possible with the use of bigger and more varied datasets in conjunction with continuous model improvement. More in-depth understanding may be possible by addressing particular issues in medical image analysis through the investigation of innovative architectures like attention mechanisms and 3D CNNs. In addition to creating criteria for model validation and performance assessment, this also involves establishing rules for bias and fairness, explaining ability and interpretability, and ensuring data privacy and security.

Jiang, Xiaoyan, Zuojin Hu, Shuihua Wang, and Yudong Zhang examined Deep Learning's involvement in medical image-based cancer diagnosis [0]. The article covers five uses of Deep Learning in cancer detection. Future research is enhancing the creation of a library of public cancer

standards, strengthening deep neural network-based models, and exploring Few-Shot learning.

The paper “DCSAU-Net: A deeper and more compact split-attention U-Net for medical image segmentation”[0] describes a novel encoder-decoder architecture for medical image segmentation. It combines the PFC method and the CSA block, keeping primary properties while emphasizing key ones. The model beats previous SOTA models in F1-score and mIoU metrics, particularly for multi-class and complicated pictures. The next focus will be on fine-tuning and optimizing the architecture for 3D medical image segmentation applications, with an emphasis on processing efficiency and scalability.

8. Conclusion:

In this paper, we provide an in-depth review of CNN methods and how they are used in medical imaging. CNNs are positioned to play an increasingly important role in expanding the field of medical imaging as research continues to solve obstacles and explore synergies with other technologies. Convolutional Neural Networks are transforming medical imaging and bringing in a new age of improved diagnostic capabilities. Their integration might have a profound influence on healthcare by paving the way

for more effective treatment plans and particular therapies. The segmentation and classification of images using CNN techniques are covered in this review research. Also covered the most current advancements in illness detection applications.

References

- Abunasser BS, Al-Hiealy MRJ, Zaqout IS, Abu-Naser SS. “Convolution Neural Network for Breast Cancer Detection and Classification Using Deep Learning.” *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev.* 2023 Feb 1;24(2):531-544. doi: 10.31557/APJCP.2023.24.2.531. PMID: 36853302; PMCID: PMC10162639.
- Ansari Y, Mourad O, Qaraqe K and Serpedin E (2023) Deep Learning for ECG Arrhythmia detection and classification: an overview of the progress for the period 2017–2023. *Front. Physiol.* 14:1246746. doi 10.3389/fphys.2023.1246746
- Bokade A, Shah A (2023) Breast Cancer Diagnosis in Mammography Images Using Deep Convolutional Neural Network-Based Transfer and Scratch Learning Approach. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology* 16(18): 1385-1394. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v16i18.39>

- Jiang, Xiaoyan, Zuojin Hu, Shuihua Wang, and Yudong Zhang. 2023. "Deep Learning for Medical Image-Based Cancer Diagnosis" *Cancers* 15, no. 14: 3608. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers15143608>
- Nadkarni, Swati, and Kevin Noronha. "Breast cancer detection using an ensemble of Convolutional Neural Networks." *International Journal of Electrical & Computer Engineering* (2088-8708) 14, no. 1 (2024).
- Pouria Rakhshan "Breast Cancer Detection Based on CNN And Federated Learning Using Embedded Devices," Mälardalens University School of Innovation Design and Engineering
- Qing Xu, Zhicheng Ma, Na HE, Wenting Duan, "DCSAU-Net: A deeper and more compact split-attention U-Net for medical image segmentation," *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, Volume 154, 2023, 106626, ISSN 0010-4825, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compbiomed.2023.106626>.
- Raimundo, João Nuno Centeno, João Pedro Pereira Fontes, Luís Gonzaga Mendes Magalhães, and Miguel Angel Guevara Lopez. 2023. "An Innovative Faster R-CNN-Based Framework for Breast Cancer Detection in MRI" *Journal of Imaging* 9, no. 9: 169. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jimaging9090169>
- Raimundo, João Nuno Centeno, João Pedro Pereira Fontes, Luís Gonzaga Mendes Magalhães, and Miguel Angel Guevara Lopez. 2023. "An Innovative Faster R-CNN-Based Framework for Breast Cancer Detection in MRI" *Journal of Imaging* 9, no. 9: 169. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jimaging9090169>
- Rana M, Bhushan M. Machine learning and Deep Learning approach for medical image analysis: diagnosis to detection. *Multimed Tools Appl.* 2022 Dec 24:1-39. Doi: 10.1007/s11042-022-14305-w. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 36588765; PMCID: PMC9788870.
- Shah, A.A., Malik, H.A.M., Muhammad, A. et al. Deep learning ensemble 2D CNN approach towards the detection of lung cancer. *Sci Rep* 13, 2987 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-29656-z>
- Unaiza Sajid, Rizwan Ahmed Khan, Shahid Munir Shah, Sheeraz Arif, "Breast cancer classification using deep learned features boosted with

- handcrafted features,” *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, Volume 86, Part C, 2023, 105353, ISSN 1746-8094,
- Wahengbam, M., Sriram, M. (2023). MRI Lung Tumor Segmentation and Classification Using Neural Networks. In: Singh, S.N., Mahanta, S., Singh, Y.J. (eds) *Proceedings of the NIELIT's International Conference on Communication, Electronics and Digital Technology. NICE-DT 2023. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 676. Springer, Singapore.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-1699-3_42
- Wu, Xin, Yue Feng, Hong Xu, Zhuosheng Lin, Tao Chen, Shengke Li, Shihan Qiu, Qichao Liu, Yuangang Ma, and Shuangsheng Zhang. “CTransCNN: Combining transformer and CNN in multilabel medical image classification.” *Knowledge-Based Systems* 281 (2023): 111030.
- Yang, L., Peng, S., Yahya, R.O. et al. Cancer detection in breast cells using a hybrid method based on deep, complex neural network and data mining. *J Cancer Res Clin Oncol* 149, 13331–13344 (2023).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00432-023-05191-2>
- Zhan, Xiangbing, Jun Liu, Huiyun Long, Jun Zhu, Haoyu Tang, Fangfang Gou, and Jia Wu. 2023. “An Intelligent Auxiliary Framework for Bone Malignant Tumor Lesion Segmentation in Medical Image Analysis” *Diagnostics* 13, no. 2: 223.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics13020223>
<https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2021/01/image-classification-using-convolutional-neural-networks-a-step-by-step-guide/>
<https://medium.com/@draj0718/convolutional-neural-networks-cnn-architectures-explained-716fb197b243>